

Internet of Things: exploring the opportunities and challenges for digital business

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Executive Summary

The report presents some of the outstanding opportunities and challenges presented by the internet of things in the 21st century. The first section provides an overview of how the connectivity between the physical and virtual worlds takes place. The structure of the internet of things is well outlined in this sector. The second section highlights the opportunities that the internet of things presents in different industries. Some of these opportunities are in sectors such as manufacturing, transportation, public sector, energy and utilities and the healthcare sector. Evidently, the internet of things has increased the level of efficiency, reduced costs and created new possibilities in each sector.

The third section of the paper outlines the main challenges posed by the internet of things such as compromised security and privacy, algorithmic setbacks, communication constraints, difficulties in data analytics and the lack of appropriate standards. After the literature review, a detailed poster presents the background and consequences of the internet of things and some recommendations on how to maximize the use of its functionalities. In the last section, there is a reflection on the learning and practice of the internet of things in this module.

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Internet of Things

Introduction

The Internet of things denotes an established network of physical objects embedded with different devices such as sensors, software, and electronics in specified network connectivity. The network connectivity empowers the objects to be able to collect and transmit data. With the Internet of things, it has proven possible to connect the virtual and physical world. The internet of things makes it possible to sense and control objects remotely as long as they are on an existing network infrastructure. According to Weber

(2016), computer-based systems and the physical world have registered the highest level of connectivity resulting in numerous benefits. In 1999, experts popularized the initial concept of the internet of things. Radio-frequency identification (RFID) served as the prerequisite for the internet of things. At the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, RFID played an important role in the auto-identification centre.

Overview and Structure of the Internet of Things

O'Brien, (2016) is keen to note that the primary concept of the internet of things was that having identifiers for each object and linking them to a certain network infrastructure would make it possible for computers to monitor and manage the objects closely. The next big concept that emerged was the tagging of objects using Bluetooth, Barcodes, digital watermarking, and near field communication. In the twenty-first century, numerous applications of the internet of things have emerged. Particularly, internet of things relies on complementary technical developments that result in various capabilities that have the potential to close the gap between the physical and the virtual world. Weber 2016 describes some of the common capabilities as identification, sensing, localization, communication and cooperation, impeded information

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processes, as well as user interfaces. The internet of things relies on the RFID for the identification process and sensors for data collection.

In the view of Hancock & Hancock (2016), the sensors have the capacity to take note of changes registered by physical objects. Smart technology is of critical importance in the internet of things as it devolves processing capabilities to various parts of an existing network infrastructure. Nanotechnology empowers small objects to exhibit connectivity to the network. Weber (2016) is clear on the fact that understanding the structure of the internet of things is of critical importance before outlining the opportunities it presents.

The internet of things must have a gigantic network that brings together computers and different devices with a form of connection using a wireless network or RFIDs. The tagging of objects using RFID takes place in real-time (Hancock & Hancock 2016).

Sensors have the capacity to fill different objects and project data concerning the physical

changes of the object. In the modern day, smaller objects have gained the capacity to become part of the gigantic network through Nanotechnology.

The internet of things has varied levels with different capabilities. The lowest level yields raw data without any form of interpretation. The second level yields information specific to questions such as Who, When, What, and Where. The third level provides knowledge and can address the how questions. The fourth level enhances understanding by answering why questions. The highest level represents wisdom, which is because of evaluated understanding. It is imperative to recognize that the number of devices linked to a certain network determines the real potential of the internet of things. Through instrumentation, it is possible to carry out simple remote monitoring and obtain raw data. Advanced remote monitoring provides diagrams and reports through information fusion. Automatic failure detection uses insight to depict correlations and patterns through batch analysis. Predictive maintenance plays the role of forecasting by

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making predictions using online analysis and prediction. Finally, autonomous adaptation is responsible for yielding knowledge by establishing cause and effect relationships through embedded analytics. These levels represent the enormous opportunities that the internet of things provides.

Opportunities Presented by Internet of Things

Weber (2016), as well as Gale (2016), have appraised the importance of the internet of things in the twenty-first century. Particularly, the new capability to connect the physical and virtual world has become useful in different sectors. The internet of things is transforming different industries in the economy. Currently, the manufacturing sector has embraced the internet of things at a remarkable speed. Between 2013 and 2014, there was a 204% increase in the use of machine-to-machine connections in manufacturing. The finance and insurance sector has also embraced the internet of things. Other industries include media and entertainment, home monitoring, hospitality, transportation and distribution, energy and utilities, public sector and smart cities, as well as the healthcare industry. In the manufacturing sector, smart products have emerged using the internet of

things.

The manufacturing sector relies on the internet of things through simple remote monitoring, as well as advanced monitoring as Schug (2016) highlights. The purpose of the monitoring is to carry out successful tracking of assets such as stock and raw materials. Machines have embedded sensors, making it easier to monitor the different machines and automatically detect any issues with the machine. Other sensors promote the level of accuracy in analysing results. The fusion of data using different sensors allows the analysis of such data to be successful. Manufacturers have been able to increase productivity by using sensors to determine

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any causes of failures and address them before they can disrupt production. Evidently, the internet of things allows manufacturers to develop highly sustainable systems that reduce wastage, cut down costs, and limit the level of human intervention.

In his article, Lacey (2016) highlights that in transportation and distribution, there are numerous opportunities created by the internet of things. Particularly, the development of the smart vehicles with numerous sensors is a breakthrough in transportation. Intelligent transportation has become a reality in the twenty-first century. Vehicle-to-vehicle communication, closely monitored navigation, adaptive cruise control, fleet management, toll collection, trip planning, passenger information, safety systems, traffic signs, travel assistance and intermodal communication represent some of the opportunities in intelligent transportation. Weber (2016) concurs that there are new possibilities for the connected vehicle evolution through audios and videos, telematics, and diagnostics. It is possible to promote safety on the roads through the advanced safety vehicle that has more than 28 different sensors. These sensors notify the driver of any changes in the vehicle that may result in an accident or affect its functionality. With these sensors, it is possible to prevent any adverse events associated with vehicles. It is possible to gain a deeper understanding of how to use cars through the sensors. Autonomously driving vehicles have become a new possibility in the recent past. The use of the internet of things in the transportation system has led to reduced fuel costs, a higher level of sustainability and

safety, as well as faster distribution systems.

Gale (2016) explored the importance of the internet of things in the energy and utility sector. It is possible to extend the lifespan of electricity infrastructure using the internet of things. Moreover, telematics has become important applications of the Internet of things in the energy sector. Remote monitoring through smart meters is now a reality in some countries. Manual

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meters did not have the desired level of accuracy, explaining why the use of smart meters has transformed the energy sector. Through remote monitoring, it is possible to have a better understanding of capacity, demand, and supply as well as the visualization on how to meet such demands. It is possible to provide recommendations on how to save energy using batch analysis.

In the public sector, the internet of things can register a higher level of efficiency in service delivery. In the view of Boos et al. (2013) the internet of things increases the participation of citizens, and it has become helpful in the development of protection of infrastructure and establishing crime control systems. For the first time, municipal leaders have the opportunity to develop safer and monitored communities. The internet of things makes it possible to monitor overcrowding, parking spaces, as well as municipal energy costs. There is evidence that the internet of things has transformed the healthcare sector, and it is likely to create new possibilities in the future. It is possible to carry out real-time monitoring of physiological changes in the body and transform service delivery using various sensors. Eagle (2016) highlights that machines used in intensive care units can have sensors and be able to monitor the progress of patients. The internet of things allows surgeons to carry out surgeries using robotics while they are far away. Diagnostics have become easier with the availability of the internet of things. Other opportunities of the internet of things include intelligent building, smart home development, traffic management, natural disaster warning, infrastructure monitoring, food and drug tracking, emergency response systems, as well as economical agriculture and breeding. In every aspect of human life, the internet of things presents a valuable opportunity.

Challenges of the Internet of Things

As Sharron and Tuckett (2016) highlight, one of the greatest challenges associated with the internet of things is security and privacy. The connectivity of the physical and virtual world poses a great threat to security. Peppet (2014) agrees with Sharron and Tuckett 2016 on the fact that the design of most of the existing code bases did not give attention to security. For this reason, connectivity to an open network is vulnerable to cyber threats. Smilansky (2016) expresses concerns about the privacy of citizens that the increasing connectivity between the physical and virtual world have compromised. All these scholars have addressed the privacy risks associated with the internet of things. With the numerous applications of the internet of things, technical challenges have proven to be a reality. The understanding of data collected through different sensors requires expertise. The need to establish a level of standardization has also become a major concern.

The need to port existing code bases and ensure that they remain functional in different network environments requires a high level of technical expertise (Sharron and Tuckett 2016). Algorithmic challenges have become evident due to the enormous sizes of data gathered by single sensors. It may be impossible to analyse data successfully when there are numerous batches of data. Distributed data analysis also mandates experts to develop an effective technology of analysing the resulting data. With the existence of different data centres and cloud computing, there is a need for effective distribution of data to various storage devices. There is also a need for proper algorithms that can analyse streaming data. Communication-constrained scenarios have also become a major challenge in the internet of things. Devices may fail to communicate effectively, or limitations of bandwidth may occur, posing critical challenges (Sharron and Tuckett 2016). The cost of maintaining communication systems is remarkably high,

introducing new expenses. Issues related to software complexity and power supply have also become priorities that need addressing in the implementation of the internet of

things.

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Reflection on Learning and Practice throughout the Module

Throughout the module, I learned important aspects of the internet of things. I gained familiarity with the new possibilities of digital business applications as well as the use of the internet of things in the collection of data, analysis, as well as the presentation of knowledge and information. According to the Gibbs' Reflection Cycle, reflection comprises of descriptions, feelings, evaluation, analysis, conclusion, and action plan. The module introduced different concepts of digital applications. One of these concepts was the internet of things. Initially, I felt overwhelmed by the numerous applications of the internet of things. I could not believe that the internet of things had ultimately connected the physical and virtual world. However, on evaluation, I recognize that there are numerous benefits of the internet of things.

The recent developments in technology have a transformative power in our society. It is possible to connect different devices and objects. It is possible to establish proper monitoring and tracking systems and gain an in-depth understanding of all the objects in the environment. With the numerous digital applications in place, it is clear that the internet has transformed the world. It is possible to reduce costs in different sectors using digital applications. The most important aspect that I learned is that each sector should maximise the benefits of the internet of things and other digital applications. With the current progress in the use of different applications, businesses can benefit if they invest in modern technology.

The internet of things can help businesses cut operating costs and register higher levels of efficiency in service delivery. It is apparent that each sector needs to undertake research to determine the potential applications of the internet of things. The module helped me appreciate all the opportunities that the internet of things provides. However, I am also aware of the

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potential challenges that businesses may encounter when using different digital applications. For this reason, there is a need to maximise the benefits of the internet of things and develop strategies for addressing the challenges. I intend to focus on in-depth research on how to resolve some of the technical challenges associated with digital applications. In my view, the module was highly successful.

Conclusion

Undoubtedly, the internet of things is the greatest innovation in the 21st century. Future predictions indicate that more than 50 billion devices will have connectivity to the internet by 2020. As expected, scholars will need to address some of the leading challenges associated with the internet of things to maximize the benefits. Security and privacy are critical concerns that need urgent addressing. Moreover, the lack of standardization and other challenges are the focus of many studies in the modern day. The applications of the internet of things are likely to increase in the future, allowing businesses to register efficiency, cut costs, and meet customer needs.

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